

NOTES

Polarographic Studies of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) and Cadmium(II) with Oxalic Acid and Succinic Acid as Primary Ligands and 2-Amino-3-hydroxypyridine as Secondary Ligand

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STUDIES on mixed ligand complexes of metal ions associated with life processes and environment, are of interest. While stability constants of 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) with different metal ions have been studied pH-metrically^{1,2} and polarographically³, literature survey indicates that no work has been carried out on the mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} with AHP as a secondary ligand and oxalic acid (OX) and succinic acid (SUCC) as primary ligands. The same is reported in this study using polarographic technique.

Experimental

AnalaR grade chemicals were used to prepare Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, OX, SUCC and AHP solutions in double-distilled water. KNO₃ was used as a supporting electrolyte and to maintain ionic strength at $\mu=0.1$ M. A 0.001% gelatin was used as the maximum suppressor. pH was adjusted with dilute HCl or NaOH to 9.5. The temperature was maintained at 30±0.1°. The polarograms were recorded after deaeration of the test solution with O₂-free nitrogen using a Toshniwal CLO2 instrument. The capillary characteristics were: $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.43 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at $t=3.0$ s, $h_{\text{corr}} = 40$ cm in 0.1 M KNO₃.

Results and Discussion

To determine the stability constants of the Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes with primary ligands (OX and SUCC), the concentration of the latter was varied from 1.1 to 0.5 M; and for the complex with secondary ligand (AHP) the concentration of the latter was varied from 0.1 to 0.6 mM. In each case a well-defined two-electron reversible reduction wave was observed which was found to be diffusion-controlled from the constancy of $i_d / h_{\text{eff}}^{1/2}$. Method of DeFord and Hume⁴ was used for determining the composition and stability constants. An analysis of $Fj[X]$ functions revealed formation of complexes ML₁ and ML₂ in each case; the stability constant values are given in Table 1.

Polarograms of ternary systems Cu—OX—AHP, Cu—SUCC—AHP, Cd—OX—AHP and Cd—SUCC—AHP were recorded by varying AHP concentration from 0 to 0.6 mM at fixed concentrations (0.2 and 0.5 M) of OX and SUCC. In this case also the wave was found to be diffusion-controlled and reversible involving two electrons. $E_{1/2}$ values in ternary systems shifted to more negative values compared to those for the binary systems. Method of Schaap and McMasters⁵ was used for the determination of composition and stability constants of mixed ligand complexes; stability constants of different mixed ligand complex species are also given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE BINARY AND MIXED COMPLEXES

$\mu=0.1$ M KNO₃, pH=9.5, Temp. = 30±0.1°

System	Stability constants			
	β_7	β_{11}	β_2	β_{12}
Cu—OX	4.70	—	8.82	—
Cu—OX—AHP	—	31.45×10^{11}	—	3.31×10^{11}
Cu—SUCC	2.60	—	4.30	—
Cu—SUCC—AHP	—	7.87×10^{10}	—	2.66×10^9
Cu—AHP	6.50	—	11.96	—
Cd—OX	2.60	—	4.66	—
Cd—OX—AHP	—	45.8×10^9	—	6.67×10^9
Cd—SUCC	1.90	—	3.28	—
Cd—SUCC—AHP	—	22.6×10^9	—	—
Cd—AHP	6.04	—	10.90	—

In case of Cd—SUCC—AHP system β_{12} was negative, indicating that this species is not formed. For a comparison of the stability of simple and mixed complex species, it is convenient to calculate mixing constant $\log K_m$ using the relation⁶,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 (\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20})$$

The positive values 3.01, 2.67, 2.82, 3.21 for Cu—OX—AHP, Cu—SUCC—AHP, Cd—OX—AHP, Cd—SUCC—AHP systems respectively, indicate that mixed complex species 1 : 1 : 1 is more stable than the binary 1 : 1 species. The stability constant values of 1 : 1 : 1 complex species in each case (Table 1) follow the order, Cu^{II} > Cd^{II}. Smaller size of Cu^{II} (87 pm) than Cd^{II} (97 pm)⁷ would tend to facilitate formation of more stable complex. This is also consistent with the findings of Irving and Williams⁸ and Maley and Mellor⁹ who concluded that Cu^{II} complexes are more stable than Cd^{II} complexes irrespective of the nature of the ligand involved.

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